

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MYCOBIOTA OF FOREST ECOSYSTEM OF SOME REGIONS OF AZERBAIJAN AND ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS CAUSED BY IT

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Abstract

Our goal is to study the mycological state of forests in the regions of Azerbaijan. More than half of the study was carried out in all districts of the city of Shirvan. During the study, pathogenic fungi were discovered on the trees. Under the influence of pathogenic fungi, pathological processes occur in plants, accompanied by disruption of the structure, physiological functions of the plant, its individual parts, for example, the formation of growths, influxes, assimilation, enzymatic activity, impaired growth, development, and death of affected tissues.

Keywords: bacteria, ecology, forest ecosystem, pathogenic fungi

INTRODUCTION

Mushrooms are not only the most important plant symbionts, without which the green world around us could not have arisen, but also terrible enemies of agricultural crops. They are diverse, destructive and affect almost all useful plants known to us. How pathogenic fungi live and how they can be combated in nature and agriculture. They infect forest trees and this has a very negative effect on forest ecology. Fungi and plants are ecologically closely related organisms. They often exist in symbiosis - mutually beneficial cohabitation. Fungi colonize the root system of plants and supply them with necessary substances and microelements from the soil, and the plants share hydrocarbons produced as a result of photosynthesis with the fungi. It is believed that once without this symbiosis, plants would not have been able to come out of the sea onto land and successfully colonize it. In addition, saprotrophic fungi decompose plant debris: if there were no fungi, the entire planet would be littered with undecayed plants [1].

Forest ecosystems play an important role in human life. We know that people prefer forests for relaxation and fresh air. Therefore, protecting forests and the health of the trees growing there is very important to us. We decided to conduct this study to find out the extent of their mycological condition. The purpose of our research was to study the mycological state of the forests of Azerbaijan. During the study, pathogenic fungi were also discovered in the forests. Among them were carriers of infectious diseases. Environmental condi-

tions can significantly influence the development of infectious diseases, either directly or through the trees they infect. The development and spread of the disease, the emergence of a source of infection leads to the accumulation of a large number of infectious agents in dead, drying and intermediate host plants. Soil, plant stumps, pots and cuttings are also characterized as one of the sites of infection [2]. Organisms with a biotrophic lifestyle, primarily fungi, can cause diseases of completely healthy plant tissues. On the other hand, those with a polytrophic lifestyle tend to accelerate the destruction of infected tissue or the plant as a whole, infecting trees and shrubs, which are usually weakened or mechanically damaged. Many bacteria and fungi lived in dead plant tissue and moved around the plant, destroying tissue that was adjacent to their toxic metabolites (toxins) [3].

During the study, special microbiological methods were used to identify fungi. When separating macromycetes, the fruiting body formed by the fungus in the plant was used, i.e. basidioma. The fruiting body was used to obtain a pure culture in the laboratory after possible certification. To do this, small parts are cut off from the membranous part of the fruiting body with a sterilized lancet and transferred to a nutrient medium, and as the colony forms, it is transferred to a new medium. The process continues until a homogeneous colony is obtained. A visible part of the micromycetes was either washed and transferred to a nutrient medium, or this part of the fungal plant was transferred to a nutrient medium to obtain a pure culture (pic.1)

Picture 1

Below is information about some of the mushrooms found during the study.

Avicularia versicolor. When growing on the lateral surfaces of the substrate, fan-shaped, semi-prostrate, attached by a narrowed base, arranged imbricately; on the upper surfaces - growing one from the middle of the other, they form lush rosette joints up to 200 mm in diameter. The surface is wavy, radially folded, distinctly velvety-pubescent, painted in concentric zones in various colors and shades: blue-black, dark brown, brown, red-brown, ocher, brown, bluish, gray in various combinations [4]. As a rule, the fruiting bodies

on one mycelium are colored more or less uniformly, but in different genets (individuals) the color can vary greatly: from a rich black and blue to a combination of pale brown tones. Old and dead overwintered fruiting bodies are sometimes covered with a layer of cyanobacteria, which gives them a green color. It grows in large colonies on dead wood of deciduous trees, rarely on conifers [5]. It usually inhabits stumps, branches and trunks that have fallen to the ground, and can also be found on living weakened trees. Distributed everywhere. Causes white rot (pic.2)

Picture 21. *Avicularia versicolor*

Coniophora puteana. The fruiting bodies are mostly annual, sometimes perennial, prostrate, resupinate, 0.5 – 1.5 mm thick and capable of growing up to 30 cm in diameter. At a young age they adhere tightly to the substrate, but in old age they peel off. The surface is initially smooth, brownish-yellow, then unevenly lumpy, tobacco-brown, always with olive tints and sometimes with a gray coating. At the base

there is dense white or cream litter. The edge is quite wide, 10–20 mm, lighter than the main part of the fruiting body or almost white, fringed, with thin fan-shaped branches [6]. It grows on stumps, dead trunks, and branches of many coniferous and deciduous trees. Sometimes found on living, weakened trees. It settles in buildings and structures, being one of the types of house mushrooms. Causes brown rot (pic.3).

Picture 3. *Coniophora puteana*

As a result, it was concluded that a high pathogenic potential of fungi involved in the formation of the mycobiota of trees and shrubs involved in the formation of forest ecosystems in the regions of Azerbaijan was identified. Approximately 72% of registered fungi have high pathogenic activity [7].

Wood decay fungi are any type of fungi that break down damp wood to rot. Fungal growth occurs due to excess water in the wood. There are white, brown and soft rot. Based on this, mushrooms can be classified according to the destruction they cause. White and brown rot are mainly caused by basidiomycetes, and soft rot by ascomycetes. For example, the bordered polypore fungus lives on dead trees, causing brown rot, and the Armillaria honey fungus lives on living trees, leaving white rot. By secreting enzymes, fungi decompose various components of the cell wall. For example, some fungi can destroy cellulose and hemicellulose, others lignin, and still others - both. Thus, each of them occupies a specific ecological niche, different from the others. Brown rot fungi destroy cellulose and hemicellulose through a complex set of oxidative reactions and the action of endocellulases. One of the stages is the

oxidation of cellulose with hydrogen peroxide, which is formed during the decomposition of hemicellulose. Lignin remains in the plant cell wall, but is subject to modification—demethylation. White rot fungi break down lignin, leaving behind cellulose; some destroy both lignin and cellulose. When decomposing lignin, these fungi use laccases, phenoloxidases and peroxidases. Lignin utilization in forest ecosystems plays an important role in carbon cycling. Soft rot is formed by the action of cellulases secreted by certain fungi on wood. The decomposition of cellulose fibers leads to the formation of microscopic cavities, causing the wood to lose its shape [8].

Of course, not all relationships with mushrooms are mutually beneficial. There are many parasites among fungi, and although some fungi have learned to parasitize animals and humans, most of them infect plants. Cultivated plants suffer most from weeds, followed by insects and microorganisms. Among microorganisms, about 80% of crop losses are caused by fungi.

Currently, about 10 thousand species of parasitic fungi are known from different, unrelated taxonomic

groups. In fact, there are even more of them: not all species are discovered and described. Most parasitic fungi are microorganisms belonging to the division of ascomycetes, or marsupial fungi. Those mushrooms that we collect in the forest for food usually represent another division - basidiomycetes. Among them there are also microscopic phytopathogens, but among the parasitic fungi that are important for agriculture, the majority are marsupials [9].

Conclusion

The lifestyle of parasitic fungi is extremely diverse. Some of them attack only one host plant species, and there are even some that can attack certain plant varieties but not other varieties of the same species. There are pathogens that cause damage to several species of closely related plants, and those that have virtually no substrate specialization and can infect several dozen plant species. A dependence is often observed: the narrower the specialization, the more aggressive the pathogen.

Pathogenic fungi interact with different plants in different conditions: terrestrial or aquatic ecosystems, agricultural ecosystems, in different climates, so the forms of interaction are also diverse. Obligate parasites (biotrophs) feed on living plant tissue. Their biochemistry and physiology are designed to penetrate the plant tissue and, without killing it, and sometimes even slightly stimulating the growth and activity of cells, consume the host's nutrients. Eventually the plant's growth slows, tissues die, and the parasite accelerates this process, but in the initial stages it is not beneficial for the biotrophs to kill the plant, and this relationship may slightly resemble a mutualistic symbiosis. On the contrary, necrotrophic fungi kill the plant and feed on already dead tissue. They are similar to saprotrophs - these are scavenger fungi that feed on dead plants that have died for other reasons. Bacteria infect the vascular system, causing first the formation of cracks, blackening, tissue deformation on the roots, stems, and trunks, then the development of tumors, which at times reach enormous sizes of several kilograms. On fruit-bearing trees, the fruits show signs of the disease first as small small round spots, initially light, then turning black.

Then, in their place, bumps grow, turning into ugly warts.

In nature, the spread of the disease is facilitated by low temperatures, strong winds and heavy rains. The saddest thing is that the disease develops slowly and signs of damage can be detected several months, even a year after purchasing a seedling or cultivated tree (in rare cases, the disease develops in a couple of weeks). Large doses of nitrogenous fertilizers contribute to the development of the disease.

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